

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Kitchen Garden among Household Members of Selected Area of Bagalkot

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Abstract:- In this 21st century kitchen garden is becoming a new trend in urban community. The people are near to disease conditions. Now a day's expense is increasing and the uses of pesticides are also increasing. So, it becomes as a healthy hobby and gives pesticide free fresh vegetables. Currently research studies shows that only 20-sq. ft is only needed for 300 days vegetables for a small family. Every household members were more care about the health of their family. So, household members are the best population to make awareness about the importance of kitchen gardening. Then we can dream "Oota from our Thota". Future of a country is in the hands of their people. Healthy individuals can only dream for a developed country. In this research the researcher examines to assess the knowledge and attitude of household members of the family regarding the importance of kitchen garden in selected urban community, Navanagar Bagalkot.

➤ Aims

- To assess the existing knowledge regarding the importance of kitchen garden among household members.
- To assess the attitude regarding the importance of kitchen garden among household members.
- To correlate the knowledge and attitude regarding the importance of kitchen garden among household members.
- To find out the association of knowledge and attitude of household members with selected demographic variables.

➤ Materials and Methods

The research design selected for the study was A Non-experimental descriptive Co relational design was adopted for the study. This design was adopted to correlate the knowledge and attitude of household members regarding the importance of kitchen garden. A sample of 90 household members who fulfill the inclusion criteria. It consists of 3 sections. In that Section A: A self-administered structured questionnaire to assess the demographic variables, it consists of 11 items. Section B This includes 38 structured questions, which are categorized under three sub headings. Section C consists of 14 statements. Depicts that the correlation (r- value) between knowledge and attitude was $r = 0.040$. It shows that there is a negative linear correlation. The knowledge of the household members is low and the attitude was high.

➤ Results

The overall tool consists of maximum score of 38. The total score of knowledge regarding importance of kitchen gardening score range from 16 to 32, mean value of 23.78(62.5% of mean percentage) with SD of 3.49. The overall tool consists of maximum score of 42. The total score of attitudes regarding importance of kitchen gardening with total score of mean of 23.78(56.6 mean percentage score) with SD of 3.49 and the score range between 25-36. There was a negative correlation between the knowledge and attitudes of household members regarding importance of kitchen gardening. The variables are correlated (r – value) between the knowledge vs.

attitude is 0.040 at $p > 0.05$, so the research hypothesis H1 was rejected.

➤ **Conclusion**

The present study assessed the knowledge and attitude of household members regarding kitchen gardening. The results revealed that 75 (83.3%) of the household members have moderately adequate knowledge, 9(10%) of the household members have adequate knowledge, 6(6.7%) have inadequate knowledge. Among the total, 59 (65.6%) of them had moderately satisfactory attitude, 31 (34.4%) had satisfactory attitude and none of household members had unsatisfactory attitude.

I. INTRODUCTION

Health is a precious possession and an asset for the individual, family, community and even the nation. Only healthy people are able to put in efforts and competencies for their own as well as nations socio economic and cultural development. Health as such is not static; it is a dynamic state which exists on a continuum from optimum health to death. It gets influenced by various factors related to human biology, lifestyle, environment and resources. People need to adopt and modify various factors to sustain a state of equilibrium and there by promote, protect, regain and maintain their health¹.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research design selected for the study was A Non-experimental descriptive Co relational design was adopted for the study. This design was adopted to correlate the knowledge and attitude of household members regarding the importance of kitchen garden. A sample of 90 household members who fulfill the inclusion criteria. It consists of 3 sections. In that Section A: A self-administered structured questionnaire to assess the demographic variables, it consists of 11 items. Section B This includes 38 structured questions, which are categorized under three sub headings. Section C consists of 14 statements. Depicts that the correlation (r- value) between knowledge and attitude was $r = 0.040$. It shows that there is a negative linear correlation. The knowledge of the household members is low and the attitude was high.

IV. RESULTS

Table 1 Association of knowledge with selected demographic variables of household members.

SL NO.	Demographic variables	Categories	Sample (n=90)		Knowledge				X2	P<0.05
					<median		>median			
			No.	%	No	%	No	%		
1	Age	31-40 yr	28	31.1	21	40.4	7	18.4	7.29 Df=2, S	P<0.05
		41-50 yr	34	37.8	16	30.8	18	47.4		
		51-60 yr	28	31.1	15	28.8	13	34.2		
2	Gender	Male	31	34.4	16	30.8	15	39.5	0.73, Df=1 S	P>0.05
		Female	59	65.6	36	69.2	23	60.5		
3	Religion	Hindu	68	75.6	41	78.8	27	71.1	8.58 Df=3 S	P<0.05
		Muslim	13	14.4	5	9.6	8	21.1		
		Christian	9	11.0	6	11.5	3	7.9		
		Others	-	-	-	-	-	-		
4	Education	Primary Education	3	3.3	1	1.9	2	5.3	1.88 Df=2 NS	P>0.05
		Secondary Education	14	15.6	10	19.2	4	10.5		
		Higher Education	73	81.1	41	78.8	32	84.2		
		Nuclear	70	77.8	42	80.8	28	73.7	1.04	

5	Type of family	Joint	17	18.9	8	15.4	9	23.7	Df=2 NS	P>0.05
		Extended	3	3.3	2	3.8	1	2.6		
6	Monthly income of family	Below 3000	2	2.2	2	3.8	0	0	3.71 Df=3 NS	P>0.05
		3001-6000	4	4.4	1	1.9	3	7.9		
		6001-9000	14	15.6	7	13.5	7	18.4		
		9001 and above	70	77.8	42	80.8	28	73.7		
7	Type of occupation	Household work	28	31.1	20	38.4	14	36.8	0.68 DF=1 NS	P>0.05
		Govt. employee	10	11.1	7	13.4	3	0.78		
		Pvt. Employee	52	57.5	25	48.0	21	5.53		
8	Marital status	Married	80	88.9	47	90.4	33	86.8	1.17 DF=2 NS	P>0.05
		Unmarried	5	5.6	2	3.8	3	7.9		
		Divorced	-	-	-	-	-	-		
		Widow	5	5.6	3	5.8	2	5.3		
9	Experience in kitchen gardening	Yes	27	30.0	14	26.9	13	34.2	0.55 DF=1 NS	P>0.05
		No	63	70.0	38	73.1	25	65.8		
10	Source of information	Relatives	6	6.7	1	1.9	5	13.2	10.5 DF=3 S	P<0.05
		Peer group	2	2.2	2	3.8	0	0		
		Mass media	26	28.9	11	21.2	15	39.5		
		Agriculture	56	62.2	38	73.1	18	47.4		
11	Space availability	Front of the house	20	22.2	14	26.9	6	15.8	2.21 DF=3 NS	P>0.05
		Back side of the house	19	21.1	11	21.2	8	21.1		
		Terrace of house	48	53.3	26	50.0	22	57.9		
		Roof or balcony house	3	3.3	1	1.9	2	5.3		

Note: S-Significant at 5% level (ie., p<0.05), NS-Not significant at 5% level (ie., p>0.05).

Table 7(a) & 7(b) The chi- square analysis was carried out to determine the association between knowledge and selected demographic variables. The association between age (χ^2 – value = 7.29, df = 2) were significantly associated with knowledge at 0.05 level i.e. P <0.05, religion (χ^2 – value = 8.58, df = 3) were significantly associated with knowledge at

0.05 level i.e. P>0.05, source of information (χ^2 – value = 10.5, df = 3) were significantly associated with knowledge at 0.05 level i.e. P <0.05, The above results evidence that knowledge of household members regarding kitchen gardening are influenced by age, religion, and source of information.

Table-2 Association of attitude with selected demographic variables of household members.

SL NO	Demographic variables	Categories	Sample (n=90)		Attitude				X ² Value	P Value
					<median		>median			
			NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%		
1	Age	31-40 yr	28	31.1	14	30.4	14	31.8	1.58, DF=2 NS	P>0.05
		41-50 yr	34	37.8	20	43.5	14	31.8		
		51-60 yr	28	31.1	12	26.1	16	36.4		
2	Gender	Male	31	34.4	19	41.3	12	27.3	1.96 DF=1 NS	P>0.05
		Female	59	65.6	27	58.7	32	72.7		
		Hindu	68	75.6	36	78.3	32	72.7	1.46, DF=3	P>0.05
		Muslim	13	14.4	6	13.0	7	15.9		

3	Religion	Christian	9	11.0	4	8.7	5	11.3	S	
		Others	-	-	-	-	-	-		
4	Education	Primary Education	3	3.3	2	4.3	1	2.3	0.30, DF=2 NS	P>0.05
		Secondary Education	14	15.6	7	15.2	7	15.9		
		Higher Secondary	73	81.1	37	80.4	36	81.8		
5	Type of family	Nuclear	70	77.8	34	73.9	36	81.0	3.07 DF=2 NS	P>0.05
		Joint	17	18.9	9	19.6	8	18.2		
		Extended	3	3.3	3	6.5	0	0		
6	Monthly income of the family	Below 3000	2	2.2	1	2.2	1	2.3	1.29, Df=3 Ns	P>0.05
		3001-6000	4	4.4	1	2.2	3	6.8		
		6001-9000	14	15.6	8	17.4	6	13.6		
		9001 and above	70	77.8	36	78.9	34	77.3		
7	Type of occupation	Household works	28	31.1	18	39.1	10	22.72	8.61 Df=1 NS	P<0.05
		Govt. employ	10	11.1	8	17.4	2	4.5		
		Pvt. Employ	52	57.5	20	43.5	32	72.7		
8	Marital Status	Married	80	88.9	39	84.8	41	93.2	2.03 DF=2 NS	P>0.05
		Unmarried	5	5.6	4	8.7	1	2.3		
		Divorced	-	-	-	-	-	-		
		Widow	5	5.6	3	6.5	2	4.5		
9	Experience in kitchen gardening	Yes	27	30.0	12	26.1	15	34.1	0.68 DF=1 NS	P>0.05
		No	63	70.0	34	73.9	29	65.9		
10	Source of information	Relatives	6	6.7	1	2.2	5	11.4	6.56 DF=3 NS	P<0.05
		Peer group	2	2.2	0	0	2	4.5		
		Mass media	26	28.9	12	26.1	14	31.8		
		Agriculture program	56	62.2	33	71.7	23	52.3		
11	Space availability	Front of the house	20	22.2	14	30.4	6	13.6	4.29 DF=3 NS	P>0.05
		Backside of the house	19	21.1	10	21.7	9	20.5		
		Terrace of the house	48	53.3	21	45.7	27	61.4		
		Roof or balcony of the house	3	3.3	1	2.2	2	4.5		

Note: S-Significant at 5% level (ie., p<0.05), NS-Not significant at 5% level (ie., p>0.05).

Table 8(a) & 8(b) The chi- square analysis was carried out to determine the association between attitude and selected demographic variables. The association with religion (χ^2 – value = 1.46, df = 3) were significantly associated with attitude at 0.05 level i.e., P<0.05, type of occupation (χ^2 – value = 8.61, df = 1) significantly associated with attitude at 0.05 level i.e. P<0.05, source of information (χ^2 – value = 6.56, df = 3) were significantly associated with attitude at 0.05

level i.e. P<0.05. All the other remaining variables like age, gender, qualification, type of family, monthly income, marital status experience in kitchen gardening, space availability were not significant at 0.05 level, i.e. P < 0.05. From here we can interpret that attitude of household members are influence by some of the above demographic variables.

V. DISCUSSION

This chapter includes the discussion of the findings of the study interpreted from statistical analysis. The present study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge and attitude regarding kitchen gardening among household members in selected urban community, Navanagar, Bagalkot. In order to achieve the objectives of the study non-experimental descriptive correlational design was adopted for the present study. Non-Probability convenience sampling technique was used to select the sample. The study was conducted in Bagalkot and data were collected from 90 household members using self-administered questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge and three-point Likert scale was used to assess the attitude of the household members regarding kitchen gardening.

VI. CONCLUSION

The present study assessed the knowledge and attitude of household members regarding kitchen gardening. The results revealed that 75(83.3%) of the household members have moderately adequate knowledge, 9(10%) of the household members have adequate knowledge, 6(6.7%) have inadequate knowledge. Among the total, 59 (65.6%) of them had moderately satisfactory attitude, 31 (34.4%) had satisfactory attitude and none of household members had unsatisfactory attitude.

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